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Educational hierarchy and pedagogical-productive management in university faculty

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Abstract Educational hierarchy and Pedagogical-Productive Management (P-P.M.) in teachers are important, it is relevant to determine the minor links in order to know what is the pending task. The objective was to determine the relationship between dimensions of educational hierarchy and P-P-Management. The sample consisted of 30 teachers from different faculties corresponding to three public universities in Lima-Peru. The results were obtained by measuring the correlations with Spearman's Rho. The correlations with the Transcendence dimension (with universalism and benevolence indicators) are the lowest, being a pending task for educational managers and administrators. It was concluded that the majority of Spearman's Rho correlations are slightly higher than the intermediate level of 0.5; the highest was 0.77 for Conservation with Personal promotion; followed by 0.73 between Conservation with Openness to change; both values being with Conservation when using indicators: security, conformity and tradition.

Key words: Educational hierarchy, pedagogical management, productive management, university teachers.

Jerarquía educativa y Gestión pedagógica-productiva en docentes universitarios

Resumen La Jerarquía educativa y la Gestión Pedagógica-Productiva (G.P-P) en docentes son importantes, es relevante determinar las menores vinculaciones para saber cuál es la tarea pendiente. El objetivo fue determinar la relación entre dimensiones de la jerarquía educativa con la G.P-P. La muestra estuvo conformada por 30 docentes de diferentes facultades correspondientes a tres universidades públicas de Lima-Perú. Los resultados se obtuvieron al medir las correlaciones con Rho de Spearman. Las correlaciones con la dimensión Transcendencia (con indicadores universalismo y benevolencia) son las menores, siendo una labor pendiente para los jefes y gestores educativos. Se concluyó que la mayoría de correlaciones de Rho de Spearman son ligeramente superiores al nivel intermedio de 0.5; la mayor fue de 0.77 para la Conservación con la Promoción personal; seguido de 0.73 entre la Conservación con la Apertura al cambio; siendo ambos valores con la Conservación al emplear indicadores: seguridad, conformidad y tradición.

Palabras claves: Jerarquía educativa, gestión pedagógica, gestión productiva, docentes universitarios

Hierarquia educacional e gestão pedagógico-protutiva em professores universitários

Resumo A hierarquia educacional e a Gestão Pedagógico-Produtiva (GPP) em professores são importantes, sendo relevante determinar os vínculos menores para saber qual é a tarefa pendente. O objetivo foi determinar a relação entre as dimensões da hierarquia educacional e a P-P-M. A amostra consistiu em 30 professores de diferentes facultades correspondentes a três universidades públicas de Lima, Peru. Os resultados foram obtidos medindo-se as correlações com o Rho de Spearman. As correlações com a dimensão Transcendência (com indicadores de universalismo e benevolência) são as mais baixas, sendo uma tarefa pendente para gerentes e administradores educacionais. Concluiu-se que a maioria das correlações Spearman's Rho é ligeiramente superior ao nível intermediário de 0,5; a mais alta foi de 0,77 para Conservação com Promoção Pessoal; seguida de 0,73 entre Conservação com Abertura a mudanças; ambos os valores estão com Conservação quando se usam os indicadores: segurança, conformidade e tradição.

Palavras-chave: Hierarquia educacional, gestão pedagógica, gestão produtiva, professores universitários.

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I. Introduction

In the current context of education, a series of changes have been made to respond to the deficiencies and demands of the globalized universe; while it is true that both the educational hierarchy and the pedagogical-productive management in teachers are important, it is relevant to determine the specific dimensions that have the greatest connection, as well as to determine those with the least connection in order to know what the pending task is; with respect to such dimensions according to the appreciation of university teachers.

The educational hierarchy and pedagogical-productive management in university teachers are facing a series of institutional problems because teachers are immersed in abundant protocol activities and coordination meetings on accreditations, university licensing, leaving the productive capacity relegated; It is necessary to complement pedagogical management with learning activities related to productive activities with students, because pedagogical activities must be strengthened with productive activities, both academic and contributions that imply the production of viable solutions and alternatives to the problems of society, as well as producing tangible goods, to the extent that they adjust or adapt to the preparation and training of each student or the faculty to which they belong; considering that it must be production that solves the student's socioeconomic level in real situations and not just simulations of solutions.

Pedagogical-productive management is a fundamental task for university teachers. This management allows improving the quality of learning, increasing student motivation, optimizing teacher time, promoting research and innovation, and promoting collaboration between teachers.

Allusions to productivity

Joy (2009) mentions that productivity refers to the generation of knowledge useful to society, which translates into technological, socioeconomic or similar innovations

Martínez and Coronado (2003): It covers the production of scientific articles, books, book chapters, conference presentations, research reports, doctoral theses, etc.

Acevedo et al. (2016): It includes publications in indexed journals, books with ISBN, book chapters, conference presentations, awards and distinctions, and participation as a postgraduate thesis advisor.

Gordillo et al. (2020): It refers to the production of scientific articles, books, book chapters, conference presentations, research reports, doctoral theses, teaching materials, educational software, etc., as a result of research and teaching.

Related research

Buela – Casal, G. and López, W. (2005) refer to productivity, in connection with cultural aspects, and aspects that contribute to the development of society, providing alternatives to the problems and needs of the population, also contributing to the prestige of the university

Bravo (2017) Qualitative study with a sample of 16 people from an educational institution in Chile. The director of the high school has competencies as a pedagogical leader in the development of the institutional educational project management document.

Islands (2018), with a qualitative study with a sample of 20 teachers from an educational institution in Mexico. The objective is to examine conflicts and inconsistencies of the teachers who carry out their pedagogical management to apply the competency model in zone 50 of Tlalpan. The main conclusions are:

The teachers had difficulties in applying the competency model due to lack of training and updating. There were differences in teacher performance between those who did interpret the model and those who did not; Acosta (2017) Mixed study with a sample of 58 teachers, 3 managers and 50 students from an educational institution in Colombia. The objective is to test the leadership preparation

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exercised in the San Luis Gonzaga educational institution with a view to optimizing learning excellence. The main conclusions are:

The director exercises transformational leadership, The director is well regarded by teachers and students. The institutional climate is generally positive, but there is a good percentage of displeasure regarding interpersonal relationships.

Lermo (2018), quantitative study with a sample of 70 teachers from an educational institution in Peru. The objective is to establish the relationship between managerial leadership and organizational commitment. The main conclusions are: There is a moderate to medium positive relationship between the hierarchy that gives rise to managerial leadership and organizational commitment.

There is a moderate to medium relationship between the establishment of goals and expectations and organizational commitment. Lévano (2018) Quantitative study with a sample of 66 teachers from an educational institution in Peru. The main conclusions are: There is a significant relationship between pedagogical management and job satisfaction of teachers.

Pedagogical management is significantly related to satisfaction with supervision, identification with the organization, work itself and the physical environment.

Huamán (2018) Quantitative study with a sample of 200 people from an educational institution in Peru. The objective is to establish the relationship between management and student learning. The main conclusions were: There is a highly significant relationship between management and student learning. There is a significant relationship between management leadership and administrative management.

II. Methodological

The research was developed with a quantitative approach, with a non-experimental cross-sectional design. This research is of a descriptive correlational scope and was developed with some teachers from Peruvian universities, where the dimensions of the first variable (Educational hierarchy) are related to the second variable (Pedagogical-productive management in teachers) to determine the existence of a relationship between them.

The sampling was non-probabilistic by convenience. The sample for the present study consisted of 30 teachers from different faculties corresponding to three public universities in Lima-Peru: 12 teachers from the university with the largest number of faculties and nine teachers from each of the two universities with an intermediate number of faculties, surveyed during the year 2022.

The questionnaires were adapted according to the format of Quispe, R. (2022); to measure the coherence of the questionnaires, expert judgment was applied with approvals of 95% and 97%, for each variable mentioned in the respective order:

2.1. Pedagogical hierarchy, which was measured from the perspective of the hierarchy of human values indicated by Abella V, Lezcano F & Casado R (2017) alluding to Schwartz (1992) in a study of the hierarchy of values in youth, said questionnaire was adequate, and its reliability of Cronbach's Alpha of 0.89 was determined; so that it was enabled to measure the educational hierarchy, with respect to values. All these relationships were synthesized into four types of values:

Transcendence: universalism and benevolence.

Personal promotion: power and achievement.

Conservation: security, conformity and tradition.

Openness to change: stimulation and individuality.

2.2. Pedagogical-productive management; measured with questions developed based on five dimensions expressed by Álvarez J, Naranjo F, Silva N, & Maldonado Gudiño C. (2021) in their research used to measure the Relationship between pedagogical management and student motivation for entrepreneurial activity in an entrepreneurship program in students of the Systems Engineering

degree at a University in Ecuador; said questionnaire was adequate, and its Cronbach's Alpha reliability of 0.87 was determined

The results were obtained by measuring the correlations between variables and it was done using Spearman's Rho statistic; obtained by linking Pedagogical-productive management in university teachers with the types of pedagogical hierarchy, considering the relevance of the last variable; also the link between said dimensions, as shown in Table 1. of the Results section; showing the contrast of the four alternative hypotheses (one for each dimension of the educational hierarchy):

H1: There is a direct relationship between Transcendence and Pedagogical-productive Management in university teachers during the year 2022

H2: There is a direct relationship between Personal Promotion and Pedagogical-productive Management in university teachers during the year 2022

H3: There is a direct relationship between Conservation and Pedagogical-productive Management in university teachers during the year 2022

H4: There is a direct relationship between Openness to change and Pedagogical-productive Management in university teachers during the year 2022

III. Results

Table 1. Correlations between the dimensions of the Educational Hierarchy with Pedagogical-Productive Management (P-P.M.) in university teachers during the year 2022

	Transcendence	Personal promotion	Conservation	Openness to change	P-P.M.
Transcendence	1				
Personal promotion	0.46	1			
Conservation	0.62	0.77	1		
Openness to change	0.58	0.58	0.73	1	
P-P.M.	0.49	0.73	0.65	0.72	1

Source: Own elaboration, prepared with collected data

The results show that they are significant correlations because they are less than 0.05. The correlation values are positive, that is, all alternative hypotheses are accepted and the correlations are direct because they are positive. One of the highest Spearman's Rho values of 0.73 was obtained for the correlation between Personal Promotion with Pedagogical-Productive Management (P-P Management).

Only two correlations referring to the Transcendence dimension (with the universalism and benevolence indicators) of the Educational Hierarchy are Spearman's Rho correlations less than 0.5. The lowest of all (0.46) between Transcendence with Personal Promotion; That is to say, they are the dimensions in which those responsible for the Educational Hierarchy and the Pedagogical-productive Management in university teachers have to emphasize to raise the level of said correlation, that is, they will have to work on the indicators of Transcendence (universalism and benevolence) which may

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have repercussions on the other correlations, being a pending task in the hierarchy positions and the pedagogical-productive management in teachers in university teachers in Peru.

IV. Discussion

They were obtained by measuring the correlations with the Spearman Rho statistician. The correlations with the Transcendence dimension (with the universalism and benevolence indicators) are the lowest, being a pending task for the hierarchs. In contrast to the present study, because the work is around the user, there is the study by Vásquez & Juárez-Gutierrez (2022) who consider the importance of considering the user's satisfaction with respect to the services received.

It was concluded that most of the Spearman's Rho correlations are slightly higher than the intermediate level of 0.5; the highest was 0.77 for Conservation with Personal Promotion; followed by 0.73 between Conservation with Openness to change; both values with Conservation when using indicators: security, conformity and tradition

The results are linked to the research of Lermo (2018), a quantitative study with a sample of 70 teachers from an educational institution in Peru finding that There is a moderate to medium positive relationship between the hierarchy that gives rise to directive leadership and organizational commitment and with the studies of Lévano (2018) for being a quantitative study with a sample of 66 teachers from an educational institution in Peru, determining that there is a significant relationship between pedagogical management and job satisfaction of teachers; It is also linked to the studies on Administrative Management and Teaching Practice in a public Educational Institution as mentioned by Fernández (2021)

The present study of Educational Hierarchy and Pedagogical-productive Management in universities, during the year 2022, for which it will also be necessary to use strategies to communicate their messages in the pedagogical-productive field to favor the institutional image as indicated by Silva Herrera, R. et al., (2023). This alternative is transcendental to consider the work of education professionals, promoting an ideal university climate and the participation of the University. The result of the correlation coefficient carried out is verified, allowing to establish a relationship between Educational Hierarchy and pedagogical-productive management in universities, 2022.

In this research work it is argued that the educational hierarchy should have an impact on universities, considering the Educational Hierarchy as that which has the capacity to direct and guide its group towards goals and achievements that facilitate raising student learning. It will also serve to accompany teachers and promote values that strengthen and empower education professionals in their performance, seeking to improve learning achievement and therefore offer a quality education that includes and engages parents that transcends the educational community, through viable, useful and productive university projects, in addition to ensuring that university productivity is at an academic level; considering for the educational hierarchy the relevance of Emotional Balance and resolution strategies in personnel according to Paucar, Torres & Montejo (2021)

V. Conclusions

It was concluded that most Spearman's Rho correlations are slightly higher than the intermediate level of 0.5; the highest value for the Spearman's Rho correlation is 0.77 for Conservation with Personal Promotion; followed by the correlation of 0.73 between Conservation with Openness to change; both being values with Conservation when using indicators: security, conformity and tradition

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References

- Abella V, Lezcano F & Casado R (2017). Evaluation of Schwartz's hierarchy of human values in adolescence: gender differences and educational implications Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1413-24782017226807>
- Acosta, C.(2017). Leadership Styles in the Management of the Technical Educational Institution San Luis Gonzaga del Espinal University of Tolima Colombia (Master's thesis).
- Álvarez J, Naranjo F, Silva N, & Maldonado Gudiño C. (2021). Relationship between pedagogical management and student motivation for entrepreneurial activity: entrepreneurship course in students of the Systems Engineering degree at Uniandes, Ecuador. *Revista Universidad y Sociedad*, 13(4), 207-217. Epub August 2, 2021. Retrieved January 15, 2023, from http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S2218-36202021000400207&lng=es&tlng=es.
- Bolívar, A. (2010). How does a pedagogical and distributed leadership improve academic achievements? *Magis, International Journal of Research in Education*, 3(5), 79-106. Retrieved from: [file:///C:/Documents%20and%20Settings/ADM/Mis%20documentos/Downloads/Dialnet-ComoUnLiderazgoPedagogicoYDistribuidoMejoraLosLogr-3667779%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Documents%20and%20Settings/ADM/Mis%20documentos/Downloads/Dialnet-ComoUnLiderazgoPedagogicoYDistribuidoMejoraLosLogr-3667779%20(1).pdf)
- Bolívar, A. (1997). Leadership, improvement and educational centers. In A. Medina (Coord.): *Leadership in education*. (pp. 25-46). Madrid, Spain: UNED. Retrieved from: http://www.textosescolares.cl/usuarios/convivencia_escolar/doc/201103070200190.U%20de%20Granada.Liderazgo_Mejora_y_Centros_Educativos.pdf
- Bolívar, A. (2016). Text of the Conference at the VI International Congress on Management of Educational Centers. Published in A. Villa (ed.). *Pedagogical Leadership in educational centers: Competencies of management teams, teachers and counselors*. Bilbao: University of Deusto and Ediciones Mensajero, pp. 145-177. ISBN 978-
- Bolívar, A. (1997). Leadership, improvement and educational centers. In A. Medina (Coord.): *Leadership in education*. (pp. 25-46). Madrid
- Bravo, P.(2017). Pedagogical Leadership of the Principal and Good Practices of School Management in a Municipal School of the VI Region. Pontifical Catholic University of Chile. (Master's thesis).
- Buela – Casal, G. and López, W. (2005). Evaluation of Ibero-American scientific journals of psychology. Initiatives and current status. *Latin American Journal of Psychology*, 37(1), 211-217. 51
- Elmore, R.F. (2008). Leadership as the practice of improvement. In Pont, B., D. Nusche and D. Hopkins (Eds.), *Improving school leadership* (pp. 37-68). Paris: OECD.
- Elmore, R. (2010). *Improving the school from the classroom*. Santiago de Chile: Fundación de Chile. Retrieved from: https://fch.cl/wp-content/uploads/2012/08/Libro_Elmore.pdf
- Fernández, V. H. R. (2021). La Gestión administrativa y práctica docente en una Institución Educativa pública. *GESTIONES (Administrative management and teaching practice in a public educational institution. GESTIONES)* 1(1). <https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/15>

- Freire.S, Miranda.A (2014). Investigación El rol del director en la escuela: el liderazgo pedagógico y sus incidencias obre el rendimiento académico . Lima GRADE . Hernández, R. et al, (2010). Metodología de la Investigación. Macgraw-Hill Interamericana. (5ª ed.). México.
- Gordillo, J., Sánchez, Y., Terrones, A., & Cruz, M. (2020). La productividad académica en las instituciones de educación superior en México: De la teoría a la práctica. Scielo, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.20511/pyr2020.v8n3.441>
- Hernández, S., Fernández, C. y Baptista, P. (2010). Metodología de la Investigación. (5ª ed.). México: McGraw-Hill.
- Hernández, R., Fernández, C. y Baptista, P. (2014). Metodología de la investigación. (6° ed.). México: Mc Graw-Hill Educación.
- Hernández Sampieri, R. y otros (2010). Metodología de la investigación. Quinta edición. México: McGraw-Hill.
- Huamán. C, (2018). El liderazgo pedagógico directoral y la gestión de los aprendizajes Los estudiantes de la institución educativa Nro. 24073 Luis Alfaro Calle de Luis Alfaro Calle de Andamarca – Lucanas Región Ayacucho (Tesis de Maestría) universidad nacional de educación Enrique Guzmán y Valle Lima
- Islas, H.(2015)Gestión Pedagógica Basado en el Modelo de Competencias en el Ejercicio profesional de las educadoras en la zona escolar 50 delegaciones. Tlalpan (Tesis de maestría) Universidad Pedagógica Nacional unidad 096 D.F. Norte México. Lermo, S. (2018) El liderazgo pedagógico del director y el compromiso organizacional en la Institución Educativa Enrique Guzmán y Valle, Los Olivos – 2018 Universidad Cesar Vallejo (Tesis de maestría) Lima.
- Joy, S. (2009). ¿Qué debo hacer y cómo debo hacerlo?: productividad académica de los psicólogos académicos. Boletín de psicología, (97), 93–116. Recuperado de <https://www.uv.es/seoane/boletin/previos/N97-6.pdf>
- Lévano, Y.(2018) Gestión pedagógica y satisfacción laboral de docentes de la institución EducativaN°6059”sagrado Corazón de Jesús” Villa María del Triunfo – 2018 (Maestría) Lima.
- Leithwood, Kenneth (1994). “Liderazgo para la reestructuración de las escuelas”, en Revista de Educación, 304. Madrid, España. Pp. 31-60. Ley Orgánica 2/2006, 3 de mayo, de Educación, (BOE 4/5/2006)
- Leithwood, K. (1994). Leadership for school restructuring. Educational Administration Quarterly, 30(4), 498-518.
- Leithwood, K. (2009). ¿Cómo liderar nuestras escuelas? Aportes desde la investigación. Santiago de Chile, Chile: Fundación Chile.
- Leithwood, K. & Jantzi, D. (2006). Transformational school leadership for large- scale reform: Effects on students, teachers, and their classroom practices. School. Effectiveness & School Improvement, 17(2), 201-227.
- Luque, R.(2018) Liderazgo directivo y desempeño docente en una institución educativa Primaria Callao-2018 Universidad Cesar Vallejo (Tesis de maestría) Lima.
- Martínez, M., & Coronado, G. (2003). Indicadores para la evaluación integral de la productividad académica en la educación superior. RELIEVE - Revista Electronica de Investigacion y Evaluacion Educativa, 9(1), 45–72. Recuperado de https://www.uv.es/RELIEVE/v9n1/RELIEVEv9n1_2

Ministerio de Educación del Perú (2014). Marco de Buen Desempeño del Directivo. Lima: MINEDU.

Paucar, E. Z. G., Torres, N. A. C., & Montejo, C. V. (2021). El Equilibrio emocional y estrategias de resolución en el personal de una municipalidad. *GESTIONES (Emotional balance and coping strategies in the staff of a municipality. MANAGEMENT)* 1(1), 1-10. https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/GESTIONES_2021

Quispe, R. L. R. (2022). Propuesta de cuestionario sobre desempeño laboral e interrelaciones humanas administrado por el personal directivo de una Universidad. *GESTIONES, (Proposal for a questionnaire on work performance and human interrelations administered by the management of a university. MANAGEMENT)* 1(1). <https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/9>

Schwartz, S. H. Universals in the content and structure of values: theory and empirical tests in 20 countries. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, New York: Academic Press, v. 25, p. 1-65, 1992. https://books.google.com.pe/books?hl=en&lr=&id=z9vHEy0osBAC&oi=fnd&pg=PA1&ots=Pjpxk0gZbD&sig=dpnPaFSp7WwPCJFCGDjw10-mvK8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false

Silva Herrera, R. E., Bustamante de Ordinola, M. del P., Gonzales Ttito, Y. M., & Soplapuco-Montalvo, J. P. (2023). Aproximación a propuesta de estrategias innovadoras para mejorar la imagen institucional (Approach to the proposal of innovative strategies to improve institutional image): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13763878>. *GESTIONES*, 3(1), 1–10. Recuperado a partir de <https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/49>

Vásquez, G. E., & Juárez-Gutierrez, R. E. (2022). El Clima organizacional y satisfacción del usuario al recibir atención en una municipalidad (The organizational climate and user satisfaction in a municipality). *GESTIONES*, 2(1), 1-11. <https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/42>

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